

Building a Visual Thinking Test for Kindergarten Children

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: September 19, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: October 20, 2020</p> <p>Published: February 20, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Test, Thinking, Kindergarten Children, Visual Thinking</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4556169</p>	<p><i>The aim of the research is to build a visual thinking test for kindergarten children, and to achieve the goal of the research, a test was prepared in light of the theory (Arnheim, 1969) in which thirteen processes were identified that together form visual thinking, the test in its initial form consisted of (78) paragraphs of (6) paragraphs for each operation, application instructions and pictures for each paragraph were prepared, and then the test was applied to an exploratory random sample to ensure the clarity of the paragraphs and instructions and to adjust the testing time.</i></p> <p><i>The test items were analysed statistically after applying an individual application to a sample of (400) children aged (4-5) and (5-6) years, who were chosen by the random stratified method with unequal distribution from the six districts of Baghdad education, and the coefficients were calculated. The difficulty of the paragraphs and the distinctive strength of them and their correlation with the total degree and the sub-degree, and in light of this two items were excluded, thus the number of test items became (76) items by (5-6) paragraphs distributed over (13) processes. The validity of the test was verified by adopting the validity indicator logical and validity of the construction through some of its indicators, which are the discriminatory strength of the paragraphs and the veracity of the paragraphs, as well as the correlations between the thirteen processes, finalized with detailed instructions for the application and pictures for each paragraph to be a ready-to-use and application tool.</i></p>

Introduction

The kindergarten stage is considered a fertile stage for the formation of thinking patterns, in which the identity of the child as a thinking person is firmly established, because the mind begins to open in the first formative years, at this age stage the weight of the brain is 90% of the weight of an adult's brain, and the child's sensory organs are highly developed and development and ready to absorb raw thinking materials, thus it implied the need to establish children's thinking skills, spark their minds and formulate their ideas at this important age stage (Fisher; 2001: 1-8).

The child's brain cells are integrated and the activity increases with the increase in visual stimuli, and since visual thinking depends on the sense of sight and visual stimuli, therefore, the practice of visual thinking is very important at this stage (Razouki and Abdul Karim, 2013: 305).

Children should be aware of the use of visual media from early childhood and thus there is a need for children to be enriched with work procedures for visual thinking since early childhood years (Mathai, 2007, p. 2). Therefore, the need has become urgent to reveal visual thinking and know the aspects of progress or delay in it, depending on an accurate and objective measurement tool in judgment, according to the soundness of its procedures, in the application and the extraction of grades and how to interpret them, this is what the current research is seeking.

Research Problem:

Despite the abundance of dealing with all kinds of visual stimuli in our contemporary world, including television pictures, computer programs, signs, signs, symbols, advertisements, gestures, hand movements and objects (Moore & Dwyer, 1994: 3).

All kindergarten-age children possess visual and innate abilities to look at their surroundings, they check faces, insects and other things while they are surrounded by tools that enable them to think visually, but they are not good enough that despite the knowledge they have, so Dian Zimmerman emphasized the need to develop thinking Basri, starting in kindergarten, we will not end up with adults who feel as though they need help to understand something new at their fingertips (Yenawine, 2013,18-25).

On the other hand, the scientist roger (Spyri) found in (1960) that the brain is divided into two lobes, left and right. The left lobe of the brain is concerned with analysing ideas, especially those related to language. It is responsible for speech, logic, sequence, time, mathematics, and details. It deals with particles, while the right

lobe is related to art, music, emotional responses, intuition, images, facial recognition, summarization, memory, and interaction with faculties (Ismaily and Qushash, 28: 2018).

This is because the left and right two sides of the brain complement their function in visual thinking as it combines sensory and rational knowledge (Gennadina, 2001: 1-2) (where it was found that the most creative thinkers, according to Maslow, were the ones who achieved a merger in the practice of thinking between the left and right hemispheres of the brain, leading to a dynamic and creative thinking that includes creative cognitive features).

Mckim (1980, 27), the names of visual thinkers have been recorded in the history of innovation from Galileo, Copernicus, Leonard, and Darwin, which proves that visual thinking is an important and useful language for exploring and understanding the world, but in reality we find an exaggeration in relying on language as a tool for thinking until verbal thinking dominates on our lives are much more than visual thinking (Reed, 2010, p.1).

Arnheim expressed his concerns about the consequences of blurring visual thinking, as a result of the exaggerated focus on verbal language alone, and stressed the need for creative practice of the eye starting from kindergarten by stressing the need to learn by seeing shapes and dealing with them during visual thinking. That is because the senses begin with (Arnheim, 1969, 2-3) will lose her educational status unless it is refined.

Arnheim (ibid) agrees with (Fisher), as he stated that if children are not encouraged in the early stages of their lives, they will stop meditating and playing with ideas, as they need to develop their thinking to prepare themselves for a rapidly changing world. (Fisher, 2009:24).

But visual thinking, on the other hand, has not been taken seriously, as there are no serious attempts to measure and correct the visual thinking of a pre-school child, so the psychological field of preschool child's tests still needs to make more effort to deal with measuring and correcting the kindergarten child to fill the deficiency in this the field.

So, the problem of the current research lies in the lack of a visual thinking test prepared for kindergarten children.

Research Importance:

As seen by Snow & Hemel (2008, p.22), the process of measuring a child in kindergarten is one of the important foundations in supporting his learning, developing his general performance and improving it. It is a process inherent to the learning and teaching process, and its results provide the kindergarten teacher and those in charge of its programs with important information about the level of progress.

The child and his strengths, and the process of measurement and evaluation contributes to identifying children who need special care or educational treatment of a special kind and developing the necessary programs for them because it reflects the indicators of normal development in this important stage of the formation of the child (Al-Aasrah, 2013: 156).

As the measure is of great importance, interest in the topic of thinking and its patterns is a necessity of life, as the study of Gribas & et al. At, 1996)) that (60%) of humans think in the visual form, while (40%) thinks auditory, sensory and imaginatively, and therefore the most important thought processes come directly from our direct perception of the world around us through the sense of sight. This is also indicated by Arnheim, 1969).

The visual system is the first sensory system that provides the basis for the creation of cognitive processes (Razouki and Abdel Karim, 2013: 207), and as Nemirovsky & Nobel 1997 pointed out (that visual thinking paves the way for the practice of other types of thinking, such as critical thinking and innovative thinking, as many scientists have come to their innovations and discoveries as a result of using this type of thinking, (2016: 61-62).

Many studies of developmental psychologists have proven that children can achieve cognitive achievements before they form words using visual thinking, because pictures are formed in them before language, according to the testimony of parents that their children carry many wonderful mental achievements before they acquire the language (Reed, 2010, p. 13), and Piaget supports this in saying, "A young child knows much more than he can speak (Furth & Wachs, 1974: 11).

Second: A theoretical framework:

Two main axes were dealt with in this aspect of the research, namely:

First: Psychometrics in Early Childhood:

The evaluation of young children differs greatly from the evaluation of the elderly, this difference resulted from their learning method, as pre-school children build knowledge through interactive and concrete experiences, and practical training methods instead of abstract thinking, paper and pencil activities, so that young children learn and express their learning They have to touch and play with things, imitate stories, speak and sing, move and play in different ways.

The evaluation is also a challenge during early childhood because the child is rapidly developing, symptomatic and strongly influenced by the environment, where children grow (physically, cognitively, socially and emotionally) but not at the same pace, because two children are not alike. Each child has a unique growth rate, in addition to that there are no two children for them. Same family, cultural and experimental backgrounds (Guddemi & Case, 2004: 2-3).

Most pre-primary school children's tests fall under the section of non-verbal tests and are called "non-verbal tests" because they do not require reading and writing, are frequently used verbal instructions and communication by the examiner through the use of vocabulary that includes pictures, and supplemented with accompanying verbal instructions, requiring all.

The tests that are designed for infants and pre-school children are individually applied, as most of the tests for children under the age of six are either performance tests or oral tests, and a few of them include simple paper-and-pencil handling. The experimental process at this stage is a highly interactive social process, as it is necessary to take into account the child's environment when evaluating it, (Anastasi and Purania, 2015: 297-29). Accordingly, looking at the literature of psychometrics, he found two theoretical trends in the interpretation of psychological measurement at the beginning of the twentieth century, the first direction was represented by the theory of (classic) psychometric measurement, and the second direction was represented in contemporary theories, the theory of psychometric measurement is one of the oldest theories of measurement as it appeared at the beginning of the twentieth century. It has multiple contributions in building psychological measures and interpreting its results. This theory relies on a basic premise in building tests and measures and analysing its paragraphs, which is the distribution of individuals' scores in the trait to be measured that takes the form of a moderate curve (Tirgeson, 1958: 9).

Judgment is made on the performance of individuals by comparing it with the performance of others on the same scale used, and by this, the degree of an individual in the scale of what is defined by its meaning is explained by comparing it with standard scores obtained from the responses of the group to which that individual belongs, and most of the mental achievement tests, preparations and personality are explained by these Tareeqah (Al-Imam et al., 1990: 30).

Hence, a good test is the one that distinguishes between individuals in the measured trait (Guller, 1966, p.22). Also, the individual's score in the test or scale consists of two parts: the true score that represents the true performance of the individual and the degree of error (Farak, 1980: 238).

Then came the other direction of measurement represented by the modern theories of measurement (the direction spoken reference) that began to appear in the mid-fifties of the last century, and its emergence was linked to the emergence of the concept of learning for mastery or mastery.

It is related to the ideometric trend of measurement, which focuses on measuring the extent of the student's cognitive development by comparing his performance to an absolute level of performance instead of comparing it with the performance of other students (Abd al-Salam, 1996: 89).

This entry focuses on measuring and diagnosing the learner's achievement of knowledge, skills, attitudes, and behaviors. It relates to specific academic, educational or training content in light of absolute performance (Allam, 2005: 5). Under this trend, a number of theories are compiled, including the generalizability theory (scope sample theory) which tried to address deficiencies in indicators of validity and stability in the traditional theory (Brennan, 1983: 233).

The theory of latent traits (the theory of response to the paragraph) has emerged from it a set of models known as the models of latent features, all aiming to determine the relationship between the performance of the individual on the test (which can be observed directly) and between the characteristics or capabilities that lie behind this performance and its interpretation, and among these models, a model (Bernium) (Laserslevide), (Rush) (Allam, 1986: 102-103), and despite the development that has occurred in measurement theories such as the possibility of generalization theory and the response theory of singularity in the past two decades, the methods of classical measurement theory have a strong impact even Now (Suen, 1990: 27).

Second: visual thinking:

The term visual thinking is often associated with the study of visual thinking by Arnheim (1969), who was trained at the Gestalt psychology school in Germany in the twenties of the last century, and he was the first to use this term. He laid out the outlines of his theory in his book "thinking The visual" in which he summed up thinking as a cognitive position based on deductive actions coming from immediate experience, this approach introduced and endorsed by Gestalt psychologists. Moreover, the mental processes implicit in this type of approach are also the hallmark of how perception works. And that cognitive activity is based on perception.

Arnheim used a number of names to refer to the nature and characteristics of these processes, which are "perception of the mind", "perceptual thinking", "visual thinking (Argenton, 2015: 220).

Arnheim also refers to processes such as (active exploration, selection, assimilation of necessities, simplification, abstraction, analysis and synthesis, completion, correction, comparison, problem solving, as well as combining, separating, and putting into context).

These processes are not the prerogatives of any one mental function, as they are the way brains deal with cognitive materials at any level, this means that abstract logical thinking and visual thinking work cognitively by following similar procedures and the function of both is to understand and interpret the world, and there is no fundamental difference in this regard. Show what happens when a person looks at the world directly or sits with his eyes closed and thinks (Arnheim, 1969:13).

Visual thinking is one of the main ways of thinking that depends on the senses. Visual thinking depends mainly on the sense of sight, and as Deborah Curtis (1987) mentioned, "Everything we have told about the past and what we deal with in our environments affects our visual thinking" Moore & Dwyer, 1994: 95), agrees. This is with Gustaf's description of visual thinking that it includes accurately perceiving the visual world and re-passing the visual experience into the mind's eye, and through vision achieves a complete understanding of so we have to see first. While Arnheim believes that the mental image for him is the first source of thinking, and claims that if we cannot bring up an image of a process or a concept in our minds, we will not be able to think about it clearly (Fisher, 2009: 50-51).

As Arnheim assumed, perception represents a specific form of thinking ((visual perception is visual thinking)), depending on mental images, visual shapes or concepts, and the like. He also refused to separate them (Arnheim, 1969: 1).

Perception is often viewed as a special type of vision, as Arnheim (Mckim, Gennadina) referred to the relationship between vision and understanding that is one of the aspects of thinking, and in the context of understanding visual forms, we find that the mental processes associated with visual understanding are called visual thinking that depends on them in Understanding things and phenomena in the world, however, logical thinking occupies a large part of the process because it involves many processes responsible for converting the input data into different symbols (categories) or visual concepts, and visual thinking does not necessarily lead us to understanding, as We enable us to think of something to be imagined or sometimes to be conscious of.

Arnhiem (ibid) described visual thinking as a representational thought preceding consciousness, and it is one unit of perception and perception. Thinking can deal with perceived objects directly during vision, and when they are not present they are replaced by mental images.

So try to establish the unity of perception and perception, excluding perception. Just a collector of information about things, but rather an intelligent perception based on processes similar to those that characterize thinking, where visual thinking begins with the task of modifying the perceptual structure of perceived data based on this on abstraction and generalization. This modification or manipulation of the elements of the visual world can generate new images (mental images) and this essence of visual thinking in which the visual concept and the mental image play a major role.

Perception is the process that the mind uses to form the structure and meaning of the visual stimuli that our eyes receive, where the mind's eye initially creates an image, whether real or imaginary and perceptual images that are believed to work through dealing with these mental images and visual thinking can result in appropriate action being taken. , Which refers to the implementation of a work, and ideas can be expressed visually by representing them through drawing and transforming them into a tangible form, or they can be talked about or written down in the form of a three-action structure (Arnheim, 1969), (Mckim, 1980), (Gennadina, 2001).

When researching the methods of visual thinking for pre-school children, we find studies (Fantz,1961), (Wagan,1973) that show that children at the age of 6 months remember the faces of strangers and that the ability of children to recognize things such as faces provides the basis for visual thinking because visual thinking depends on Most of the ability to remember and process visual images, memory forms the basis for the formation of more general concepts and is also useful for visual thinking (Reed, 2010: 13).

The thinking of children visually also depends on the child's imagination, which requires facts and observations drawn from his experience in reality. They always try to express it visually by drawing. As for the beauty of a young child's thinking, it is that he is free and unrestricted, as he can transform random lines into beautiful shapes and possible pictures (Fisher, 2009, p.99).

Thus, attention of researchers attracts the wonderful activity of children and the ability to reflect the image of the world. Thinking in preschool depends on perception and action, (internal localization) the formation of internal mental structures based on understanding the structures of socially defined external activity, where children think through drawing and create a holistic graphic model of the reality. With the development of his abilities, he can distinguish the basic elements in the subject, to enrich the product of visual thinking, so their drawings improve.

When the child thinks visually he does not summarize but merges the transformed parts of the pictorial stimulus, which creates a complete picture, and through simulation the images of the imagination in this period become more complete, and the creative processing becomes More clearly, visual thinking occupies a special place in the structure of the child's general mental development, providing a general and dynamic understanding of the surrounding world (Gennadina, 2001: 34).

Third: the practical aspect:

First: The research community:

The research community is composed of the children of the governmental Riyadh subordinate to Baghdad Education, next to it Al-Karkh and Al-Rusafa for the academic year (2019/2020), whose number is (503388) children, distributed according to the six education directorates in Baghdad governorate.

Second: The research sample:

A sample of (400) children and girls from the research community was selected in a random, staged method from governmental Riyadh affiliated to the six Baghdad education directorates.

Third: The theoretical assumptions:

The theoretical premises are defined as follows:

1-The test was based on the thirteen processes that form visual thinking, which were mentioned by Arnheim (1969) in the theory of visual thinking that he founded.

2-Considering the visual thinking processes as an integrated whole unit for which a total score is calculated on the test, as Arnheim indicated that the visual thinking processes are regulated by principles, laws and work mechanisms themselves, and they have the same cognitive value, so we cannot distinguish one of them over the other, so they are of equal importance and constitute in their entirety visual thinking (ibid, 1969: 13).

3-Relying on the (classical) psychometric theory in building psychological and educational tests and standards are used, so the standard characteristics of the test and its processes will be calculated in light of the indicators of this theory.

4- Adopting the mental and experimental approach in constructing the test, as behavior is observed and measured accurately in specific situations to a large degree. In addition to the experience approach, through the use of expert opinions in some construction procedures, as well as the researcher's experience.

Fourth: Procedures for building the test:

When preparing the initial image for the test, several procedures are required:

1-Determining the components of the test: The thirteen processes mentioned by Arnheim are adopted as components that constitute a whole of visual thinking, and the following is an explanation of these three processes:

First: Active exploration is a search and investigation to refer to changes that occur in the environment when something appears or disappears, or moves from one place to another, or when the shape, size, coloration or brightness is changed (Arnheim, 1969:20).

Second: selection: where Arnheim indicated that it is possible to define a goal from the total scope of the given field and deal with it, focus on some information of interest and neglect what is secondary and less important (ibid: 25-26).

Third: Grasping of essentials: It is the careful examination of things and seeing the fine details (ibid).

Fourth: Simplification and requires reconfiguring complex concepts into simple, well-shaped forms and describing sensory perceptual patterns to a minimum of information (ibid: 79).

Fifth: Abstraction includes translating the concept into the meaning that it denotes, after defining it and extracting deductively from the context and defining the characteristic of it using the image, symbol or signs.(ibid: 8).

Sixth: analysis and synthesis: During the analysis, the elements intertwined in their structural arrangement, and the relationships forming the overall complex visual pattern to some extent, as for the power of synthesis, gives vitality and meaning to the vague, rigid forms to become understandable and clear to the events of the perfect state (ibid: 56-57).

Seventh: Completion: It is the individual's completion of the part that he does not see, that is, the completion of the missing part of the figure through the visual parts in order to produce a complete form (ibid: 34).

Eighth: Correction: is to correct or modify the wrong image in order to improve it and arrange it depending on the facts available to the observer through inferences drawn from the knowledge of the observer (ibid: 89).

Ninth: Comparison: is to distinguish between objects in terms of difference and similarity in size, color, or spatial orientation of the distinctive features of visual patterns (ibid: 66).

Tenth: Problem Solving: It is the restructuring of the problem situation, whereby the structural links within the given visual pattern are changed in a way that leads to solving the problem (ibid: 24-25).

Eleven: as well as combining: the parts are combined in order for the image to acquire its true form, so that the context is complete, in order to understand it as one unit (ibid: 66).

Twelve: Separating: It requires finding an object or certain parts of a larger context, distinguishing them spatially and separating them by difference within the elements presented (ibid: 65).

Thirteen: Putting in context Shapes should be categorized into groups according to common features between them after the traits that belong under one class are assigned (ibid:159-162).

3-Formulating the paragraphs of the visual thinking test.

In light of Arnheim's description of the thirteen processes of visual thinking, the test paragraphs were formulated by reviewing the literature visual thinking and the characteristics of the cognitive development of a pre-school child and the educational literature related to this, as well as the researcher's experience of this age stage as she is a specialist in kindergarten and works as a teacher in direct contact with them.

The number of paragraphs reached (78) paragraphs distributed among the thirteen processes, with (6) paragraphs for each operation, and the stimuli (colored pictures) for each paragraph were prepared in proportion to the nature of each of the aforementioned processes by looking at some educational sites for the early childhood stage in the network Spider (internet) in addition to the researcher's design of most of the images by using montage technology.

4-Preparation of test application instructions:

The researcher prepared instructions for the application of the test in order to standardize the instructions for all members of the sample in order to reach a good level of experimental control so that the child's score on the test is as close to what it expresses his real performance.

5-Validity of the test items (logical analysis of the paragraphs):

After preparing the paragraphs in their initial form, the test and its instructions were presented in addition to an accurate description of the processes referred to by Arnheim to a group of arbitrators specializing in childhood, measurement, evaluation and psychology, in order to verify:

A- The validity of the paragraphs in measuring each operation.

B - The extent of the suitability of the paragraphs to the level of the kindergarten child.

C- Set test instructions.

D- Amending the paragraphs that require modification.

E- Delete inappropriate paragraphs.

After collecting the observations of the experts, their observations and suggestions were taken into account, in which their agreement was reached on each paragraph, as all the paragraphs were retained and they obtained a 100% approval rate of the experts' agreement, after modifying the images of four paragraphs according to the opinions of the experts themselves.

6-The scouting experience of the test:

The test was applied to a simple random sample of (40) children, from children aged (4-5) (5-6) years, males and females, and it became clear from this experiment that the paragraphs, pictures, and instructions were clear to all children, and the time taken to answer paragraphs was calculated. The test and calculating the average response time, and the time spent in answering the test for kindergarten children ranged between (12-30) minutes with an average time of (20) minutes, and the time spent in answering the pre-school children ranged between (10-18) minutes with an average time (15) Accurate.

7-Determine the test score (correction key):

After collecting the observations of a number of experts and specialists in measurement and evaluation, the researcher found their agreement that the test score should be (0, 1) as the test items require a single correct answer, where a score (1) is given if the child answers correctly or chooses the correct alternative from among a number of the alternatives, while the degree is given (zero) when the child is unable to give a correct answer or chooses the wrong alternative from among a number of alternatives.

8-Preparing the answer sheet

The researcher prepared a form for registering the child's response to the test, which contains information about the child and also includes fields in which the child's response is recorded and the score he will obtain for each paragraph.

After all these procedures, the visual reasoning test was taken in the form of a set of cards (pictures). Each card is a paragraph that represents or measures the process that was developed in order to measure it, with detailed instructions for each process or paragraph in the answer sheet, so the test is ready to be applied to the statistical analysis sample.

Fifth: statistical analysis of the paragraphs:

Those in charge of building tests and standards are interested in writing or selecting high-quality paragraphs to accurately measure the human features, as the logical examination and expert judgments do not denote field experimentation of the test and analyze its vocabulary using statistical methods related to the difficulty level of the paragraph and its differential strength between the upper and lower levels of the characteristic that the test measures.

This is to identify the ambiguous or confusing paragraphs, which encourage guesswork, and the very easy or difficult paragraphs that do not reveal the individual differences of the feature measured by the standard reference test, and thus do not distinguish between the levels of this characteristic as it does not contribute any measure of the test's validity or consistency (Allam, 2000: 266- 267).

Therefore, the researcher applied the test individually to a sample of (400) children, in which she adhered to the necessary conditions before performing the individual test for the child in terms of providing a suitable place isolated from other children, which is characterized by relative calm and providing the factor of reassurance, as the researcher deliberately raised an atmosphere of familiarity between them And between the child and presenting the encouraging sweets so that the researcher can complete the child's test and answer all the test items without losing interest or attention in a comfortable and enjoyable atmosphere for him.

A-Paragraph difficulty coefficient: It is the ratio of those who answer the paragraph with a correct answer, and then arranging the paragraphs in terms of difficulty, as the testers start with the relatively easy paragraphs and move to the increasingly difficult paragraphs.

This gives confidence in the response of individuals to the test and reduces the likelihood of consuming a lot of Time to answer paragraphs that exceed their ability and omit the easiest paragraphs that they can answer correctly. The paragraphs that no individual can answer are paragraphs that do not add anything to the test and contribute to the reliability or validity of the test (Anastasi and Uraena, 2015: 222), so the following steps were followed to calculate Paragraphs difficulty- :

- 1-The children's overall scores on the test were arranged from the highest to the lowest.
- 2-The upper and lower 27% of the total scores were chosen to represent the two extreme groups, and the number of children in both groups was (216) children, so that the share of each group was (108) children.
- 3-The number of children who answered correctly for each paragraph of the test paragraphs in both the upper and lower groups was calculated,

Then, the paragraph difficulty factor equation was used. In order for the researcher to make the decision to judge the difficulty of the paragraph by excluding or keeping the paragraphs, the researcher determined the acceptable range of paragraphs and counting the paragraph is good When its difficulty ranges (0,20-0,80).

B - The discriminatory force of paragraphs:

It is the difference between the percentage of those who answered a correct answer on each paragraph in the upper and lower groups. Johnson (1951-Ebel, 1979-Osterhof, 1976) has described this indicator frequently in the psychometric literature (Instasi and Uraena, 2015: 236).

By following the same three steps that the researcher followed in extracting the paragraph difficulty factor, the discrimination factor was calculated for each paragraph of the test items using the discrimination equation (Johnson Equation).

The researcher adopted the Abel criterion as a guide to determine the extent of acceptance or rejection of the paragraph as the researcher made the decision to retain and accept the paragraphs that range Its discrimination coefficient is (0,30 - or more) in order to select more powerful items in the test, and it has been found that there are two items whose discriminatory strength is less than (0,30), namely (paragraph 5 of the fourth process) (and paragraph 6 of the seventh process).

It was found that the number of very good paragraphs in their discriminatory power was (59) paragraphs with a ratio of (75.6) and the number of good paragraphs with their discriminatory power (17 paragraphs and a percentage of 21.79). The number of paragraphs borderline (2) was a percentage (2.26) and no.

There is a weak paragraph, meaning that all paragraphs have the ability to distinguish with the exception of two paragraphs of Table (1).

Table (1)

Distribution of test items to levels of discrimination evidence

their ratio	their number	the names of the operations	Paragraph distinction coefficient
75,6	59	distributed over all operations	0,40, or more-
21,79	17	Select-Simplify-Abstraction-Analysis and Synthesis-Completion-Correction-Comparison-Combine-Situation in Context	0,30-0,39
2,26	2	simplification - completion	0,20 – 0,29
		none	0,19

Putting in context
Separating
as well as Combining
Problem solving
Comparison
Correction
completion
analysis and synthesis
Abstraction
Simplification
Grasping of essentials
Selection
Active exploration
Visual thinking

C - Item Validity of the paragraphs (Internal consistency):

The internal consistency of the test was calculated by calculating:-

1-The relationship between the paragraph score and the total score of the test.

2-The relationship between the paragraph score and the sub-process score.

To calculate these correlations, the original double-correlation coefficient (Point by Cyril) was used between the scores of each paragraph, the total score of the test, the score for each paragraph and the sub-score for each process after excluding paragraphs (5) from the simplification process and (6) from the completion process, so it became clear that the distinct paragraphs were Its correlation coefficient with the overall and sub-degree D when compared with the tabular value of 0.182) at the level of significance (0.01) and the degree of freedom (398), as shown in the table.

3-The correlations between the thirteen processes were calculated with some times and with visual reasoning at other times using the Pearson correlation coefficient.

Thus, a matrix of correlation coefficients was obtained, and the significance of the correlation coefficients was chosen by comparing it with the critical (tabular) values of the Pearson correlation coefficient of (0.128).

All of them are significant at the level (0.01) and at the degree of freedom (398), and thus a matrix of correlation coefficients was obtained, the values ranged between (0.749 -0.29).Table (2) illustrates that:-

Table (2)

Matrix of correlation coefficients between visual thinking processes

													1	Visual thinking
												1	0.702	Active exploration
										1	0.523	0.738		Selection
										1	0.567	0.495	0.749	Grasping of essentials
									1	0.444	0.383	0.366	0.583	Simplification
								1	0.294	0.425	0.431	0.406	0.621	Abstraction
							1	0.378	0.294	0.501	0.517	0.47	0.707	analysis and synthesis
						1	0.425	0.516	0.317	0.505	0.463	0.392	0.668	Completion
					1	0.423	0.406	0.356	0.357	0.465	0.388	0.404	0.666	Correction
				1	0.47	0.358	0.428	0.381	0.381	0.452	0.45	0.498	0.715	Comparison
			1	0.541	0.436	0.366	0.431	0.365	0.322	0.475	0.465	0.405	0.696	Problem solving
		1	0,43	0.39	0.431	0.502	0.447	0.358	0,309	0.405	0,445	0.405	0.655	as well as Combining
	1	0.391	0.463	0.459	0.402	0.439	0.464	0.354	0.349	0.478	0,445	0.424	0.707	Separating
1	0.483	0.537	0.374	0.448	0.502	0.478	0.436	0.378	0.378	0,513	0.473	0.427	0.712	Putting in context

After these procedures, which the researcher followed in studying all the characteristics related to the paragraphs, the researcher took the final decision to retain or delete the paragraphs after determining the extent to which the paragraph would be accepted, which is when the paragraph difficulty factor ranges between (0.20-0.80) and has a discriminatory power It is (0.30 or more) and has a positive and significant relationship with the total score and sub-score of the test. Accordingly, the test consisted of (76) paragraphs after it was (78) paragraphs that two paragraphs were deleted, namely paragraph (5) of the (simplification) process because of its weak power to distinguish, and paragraph (6) of the (completion) process due to its weakness and difficulty in distinguishing, then The researcher arranged the test items according to their difficulty, from easy to difficult. Table (3) illustrates this:-

Arrange the test items according to their difficulty and delete the unmarked ones in their final form.

Second, the selection process						First: the process of active discovery					
2 honesty	1 honesty	Paragraph force Differential	coefficient of difficulty	Order of paragraphs According to its	Paragraph number	2 honesty	1 honesty	Paragraph force Differential	coefficient of difficulty	Order of paragraphs According to its	Paragraph number
0,467**	0,316**	0,44	0,47	1	3	0,645**	0,455**	0,53	0,64	1	6
0,601**	0,495**	0,54	0,39	2	2	0,708**	0,537**	0,68	0,50	2	4

0,661 **	0,500 **	0,55	0,36	3	4	0,709 **	0,522 **	0,67	0,45	3	5
0,501 **	0,425 **	0,43	0,32	4	1	0,710 **	0,483 **	0,57	0,39	4	2
0,592 **	0,388 **	0,43	0,30	5	6	0,702 **	0,456 **	0,56	0,38	5	3
0,552 **	0,370 **	0,38	0,27	6	5	0,610 **	0,413 **	0,46	0,33	6	1
Fourth: the process of simplification						Third: the process of absorbing the necessities					
0,630 **	0,468 **	0,58	0,61	1	3	0,498 **	0,365 **	0,41	0,43	1	6
0,554 **	0,194 **	0,41	0,59	2	2	0,521 **	0,390 **	0,47	0,38	2	1
0,661 **	0,365 **	0,44	0,54	3	6	0,527 **	0,370 **	0,51	0,38	3	2
0,555 **	0,371 **	0,48	0,42	4	4	0,627 **	0,395 **	0,56	0,38	4	4
0,56 6	0,325 **	0,37	0,36	5	1	0,613 **	0,453 **	0,48	0,32	5	5
						0,510 **	0,395 **	0,44	0,29	6	3
Sixth: analysis and synthesis						Fifth: the abstraction process					
0,682 **	0,535 **	0,60	0,66	1	5	0,532 **	0,256 **	0,38	0,43	1	3
0,691 **	0,570 **	0,72	0,54	2	6	0,452 **	0,382 **	0,44	0,38	2	6
0,652 **	0,329 **	0,51	0,46	3	4	0,619 **	0,275 **	0,37	0,36	3	4
0,413 **	0,251 **	0,32	0,35	4	3	0,659 **	0,474 **	0,56	0,31	4	1
0,480 **	0,342 **	0,39	0,34	5	2	0,480 **	0,342 **	0,34	0,25	5	5
0,435 **	0,402 **	0,44	0,29	6	1	0,636 **	0,372 **	0,38	0,23	6	2

Eighth: the correction process						Seventh: the completion process					
0,534 **	0,316 **	0,35	0,55	1	4	0,654 **	0,484 **	0,55	0,30	1	4
0,468 **	0,299 **	0,44	0,44	2	2	0,641 **	0,442 **	0,44	0,27	2	2
0,546 **	0,314 **	0,41	0,41	3	3	0,599 **	0,400 **	0,45	0,26	3	3
0,506 **	0,317 **	0,35	0,31	4	5	0,583 **	0,281 **	0,43	0,23	4	5
0,529 **	0,448 **	0,41	0,22	5	1	0,496 **	0,353 **	0,32	0,20	5	1
0,488 **	0,353 **	0,32	0,20	6	6						
Tenth: The Problem Solving Process						Ninth: The Comparison Process					
0,664 **	0,425 **	0,50	0,55	1	4	0,561 **	0,483 **	0,43	0,77	1	4
0,563 **	0,497 **	0,58	0,54	2	1	0,581 **	0,436 **	0,39	0,76	2	5
0,692 **	0,407 **	0,44	0,54	3	6	0,679 **	0,433 **	0,55	0,46	3	6
0,746 **	0,496 **	0,61	0,48	4	5	0,738 **	0,514 **	0,59	0,40	4	1
0,590 **	0,439 **	0,51	0,47	5	2	0,737 **	0,542 **	0,64	0,37	5	2
0,679 **	0,487 **	0,56	0,40	6	3	0,720 **	0,512 **	0,60	0,37	6	3

Twelve: the separation processes						Eleven: the process of combining					
0,638**	0,429**	0,50	0,55	1	6	0,545**	0,304**	0,38	0,35	1	1
0,743**	0,543**	0,69	0,44	2	3	0,703**	0,471**	0,50	0,31	2	5
0,743**	0,565**	0,66	0,40	3	5	0,615**	0,377**	0,40	0,22	3	6
0,614**	0,410**	0,47	0,38	4	1	0,618**	0,460**	0,42	0,21	4	4
0,667**	0,477**	0,54	0,35	5	2	0,656**	0,428**	0,39	0,21	5	2
0,721**	0,492*	0,53	0,30	6	4	0,524**	0,374**	0,37	0,21	6	3

Thirteen: The Placement Process in Context					
0,520**	0,299**	0,33	0,56	1	3
0,668**	0,477**	0,52	0,36	2	6
0,608**	0,398**	0,44	0,34	3	5
0,686**	0,498**	0,44	0,27	4	2
0,558**	0,460**	0,47	0,24	5	1
0,595**	0,481**	0,44	0,24	6	4

Stability of the test:

Stability is one of the psychometric properties of a good scale, because it is not possible to obtain complete validity of psychological measures, as there are no absolute accuracy and precision measures, and it includes a degree of error, which should be calculated by the coefficient of stability as well (Farg, 1980: 332). The reliability was estimated by using the internal consistency method using the Keoder-Richardson equation (20) after applying the test to (50) children from Riyadh, and the test reliability coefficient reached (0.93).

Standard error of measurement:

The degree of the individual observed in the test differs in most of the time from his actual score due to the effect of the observed score by multiple sources of errors. The standard error of measurement is a fundamental factor in estimating and interpreting the results of tests and measures, and it is closely related to the concept of reliability (Alam, 2000: 174-179) and (Ebel) believes that the standard error of measurement is an indicator of the accuracy of the measurement because it shows how close an individual's scores on the scale are to the true degree. (Ebel, 1972, p.29).

Therefore, the standard error equation was applied to the measurement depending on the reliability coefficient by the Kioder-Richardson method, so the value of the standard error was (3.58) when the test reliability was (0.93).

Finalized test description:

After these procedures, the visual thinking test was finalized to be ready to be used individually in measuring the visual thinking of kindergarten children, the test consists of (76) test items distributed into (13) processes, the number of paragraphs of each process ranges between (5-6) items. The test contains clear instructions for applying the test to the tester with the correction key by giving a score of (1) for the correct answer, and (0) for the wrong answer, with possible correct answers for the paragraphs that are verbally answered by the child and which were deduced through the application. (38) So that the highest score that a child can get is (76) and the lowest score is (zero).

A slight amendment was made to the answer sheet in the number of designated fields in proportion to the number of items remaining after deleting two test items.

Recommendations:

Through the findings of the current research, the researcher recommends the following:

- Circulating the current test on education directorates in Baghdad and training teachers on how to implement and adhere to its instructions in order to detect children with a low level of development, and to enhance and enrich visual thinking among children who possess it in a medium or high way.
- Establishing an educational unit based on visual thinking strategies, with following up on children's cognitive, skill and emotional development, in line with Riyadh in Western countries.
- Creating technical means and interactive software in teaching kindergarten children to contribute to the development of their thinking visually.

Suggestions:

- In continuation of the findings of the current research, the researcher proposes conducting studies on:
- Building a similar test using an interactive board or a computer (a computerized visual reasoning test).
 - Codifying the current test to derive standards for the Iraqi environment as a whole.

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